

An Appraisal In Regional Imbalances In Health Care Facilities Of Purba Medinipur District, West Bengal

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Abstract

Health care means the maintenance of human health by the means of prevention of diseases. At the same time it also emphasizes on the diagnosis, treatment, recovery of both the physical and mental impairments in people. State of physical, mental and social wellbeing is known as health. Good health results in a better quality of life. Economic growth leads people to live better and longer. Longer life expectancy encourages larger investments in human capital, which in turn accelerates the per capita income. Health service is an indicator of social development. The study on health care facilities of a region is a far more fruitful exercise towards planning for development.

Purba Medinipur district, located to the southern part of West Bengal, has better health care facilities as compared to the other districts of West Bengal or other states of India. This district has quite a handful number of hospitals, block primary health centres, primary health centres and nursing homes. The number of beds for patients in various medical institutions and the number of doctors present in the district also remain higher. However, it has been found that a slight regional imbalance in the health care sector is present in the district. On further analysis, all the 25 blocks and 5 municipalities have been grouped into surplus and deficit areas based on the availability of various medical services. The study reveals a significant amount of disparity in the distribution of health services in Purba Medinipur district. This type of disparity create regional imbalances and hinders the all round development of an area. Proper planning is required for equal distribution of medical facilities and health services.

Keywords Health Care, Prevention Of Diseases, Social Wellbeing, Economic Growth, Social Development, Quality of Life, Regional Imbalance, Surplus And Deficit, Disparity.

Introduction

Development leads to advancement and it is used to describe the process of economic and social transformation. Development means the evolution of society from one state to another and more control over its environment. Economic growth does not ensure development and hence true development has to emerge from within the society – neither can be borrowed from elsewhere nor can it be imposed.

Aim of study

Objectives of this paper are to study-

1. Spatio-temporal variation of different health care facilities of Purba Medinipur district
2. Spatial variation of health services among different blocks and municipalities of the district
3. The regional disparity in health care sector of the district.

Review of Literature

Goulet (1971) highlighted three basic components in development: (i) life sustenance, (ii) self esteem and (iii) freedom. The basic needs concept was initiated in the 70s by the World Bank which aims for housing, clothing, food and minimal education for all. Hence, development means to elevate poverty and at the same time provide basic needs, to promote a social order where none is oppressed, nor is there an oppressor.

Economic growth leads people to live longer and better and enjoy good health. According to World Health Organisation (WHO), health care facilities are hospitals, primary health care centres, isolation camps, burn patient units, feeding centres and others. Health services are considered as one of the most important criteria of human development index. Good health results in a better quality of life. Higher income leads to better health and sanitation but better health and sanitation also leads to higher income because of increased productivity and labour force participation.

Methodology

The study is based on the secondary data collected from the District Census Handbook, Census of India, 2011 and from the office of Deputy Chief Medical Officer of Health, Purba medinipur. The district and block-wise data for health services (hospitals, rural hospitals, block primary health centre, primary health centres and nursing homes) have been collected, tabulated and mapped. Data on Universal Immunization Programmes for various years have also been collected. Number of people served by various health facilities have been calculated and mapped. Score values of the whole district and the blocks and municipalities of the district have been calculated and analysed. On the basis of these values, residual score values for the blocks have been found out. The surplus and deficit blocks in terms of health facilities have been calculated and tabulated.

Statistics Used in the Study

Location of The Study Area

The district of Purba Medinipur is situated between 21° 38' north and 22° 30' north latitude, and 87° 27' east and 88° 11' east longitudes. The youngest district emerged on 1st January, 2002 from former undivided Midnapore. This newly created 19th district has an area of 4295 square kilometers (District Statistical Handbook, 2005) and has a population of about 5095875 (2011 census) with a density of 1028 persons per square kilometer. The district comprises of 4 subdivisions, 21 police stations and 25 Community Development Blocks and 5 Municipalities, with the district headquarter at Tamluk – the much known Tamralipta port of the Gupta Age.

Source: NATMO and Census of India, 2011
Fig. 1

Analysis

Health care facilities

Medical facilities available in the district of Purba Medinipur have been shown in Table-1. It is seen that the number of hospitals, rural hospitals, block primary health centres and primary health centres in the district remained the same from 2010 to 2014, although,

there was a little increase in the number of nursing homes during this year. The numbers of nursing homes have been decreased from 177 in 2013 to 132 in 2014. This is because some nursing homes have not got renewal license certificate from the health department of West Bengal as they could not fulfill the criteria set by the government.

Table-1. Year Wise Medical Facilities Available In the District of Purba Medinipur, 2010-2014.

Year	Hospitals	Number of Medical Institutions					Total number of beds	Number of doctors
		Rural Hospitals	Block Primary Health Centres	Primary Health Centres	Nursing Homes	Total		
2010	5	3	22	51	152	233	3416	258
2011	5	3	22	51	152	233	3416	260
2012	5	3	22	51	144	225	3987	265
2013	5	3	22	51	177	258	4026	315
2014	5	3	22	51	132	213	3486	293

Source: Dy. C.M.O.H. - II, Purba Medinipur., Super / Director of the respective (L.S.G. / Private) hospitals, 2014.

In all these medical centres the total number of beds has grown from 3416 to 3486 which accounts only 2.1 percent growth in these five years. Total number of doctors available in the

district increased from 258 in 2010 to 295 in 2014. Therefore, it may be said that the medical facilities in the study area are not satisfactory according to the present population scenario.

Source: As in Table- 1

Fig. 2

Table-2. Achievement of Universal Immunization Programme In The District Of Purba Medinipur, 2009-10 to 2013-14

YEAR	NUMBER OF CASES				
	TT	DPT	POLIO	BCG	MEASLES
2009-10	78035	86755	84408	89338	82654
2010-11	83315	81993	83454	91489	81537
2011-12	88058	86201	70179	91795	82180
2012-13	83200	85164	78116	87735	84723
2013-14	82988	82445	88355	88430	80232

Note : TT = Tetanus Toxoid DPT = Diphtheria Pertussis Tetanus
 BCG = Bacille Calmette Guerin

Source: Deputy C.M.O.H. - III, Purba Medinipur, 2014

Various Immunization Programmes help in the development of a region. Table-2 shows that from 2009-10 to 2013-14 quite a good number of populations was covered under TT, DPT, Polio, BCG and Measles immunizing programme. As more and more industries are coming up, with the increase in literacy level and consciousness of the mass population, the usefulness of various types of immunization has been realized and this in turn is improving the quality of life.

Source: As in Table-2

Fig. 3

Table-3. Medical Facilities Available In the District of Purba Mdinipur, 2014

C.D. Block / Municipality	Number of Medical Institutions						Total Numbers of Beds	Number of Doctors
	Hospitals	Rural Hospitals	Block Primary Health Centres	Primary Health Centres	Nursing Homes	Total		
Tamluk	-	-	1	2	3	6	65	4
Sahid Matangini	-	-	1	2	8	11	115	8
Panskura	-	-	1	2	6	9	110	7
Kolaghat	-	-	1	2	9	12	145	7
Moyna	-	-	1	2	2	5	50	3
Nandakumar	-	-	1	2	1	4	50	10
Chandipur	-	-	1	2	8	11	165	5
Mahishadal	-	1	-	1	3	5	80	8
Nandigram I	-	-	1	2	-	3	46	9
Nandigram II	-	1	-	2	-	3	30	10
Sutahata	-	-	1	3	2	6	115	6
Haldia	-	-	1	2	-	3	20	5
Patashpur I	-	-	1	1	3	5	40	4
Patashpur II	-	-	1	2	1	4	40	6
Bhagwanpur I	-	1	-	3	3	7	60	5
Egra I	-	-	1	2	1	4	20	6
Egra II	-	-	1	3	-	4	50	4
Khejuri I	-	-	1	1	-	2	40	6
Khejuri II	-	-	1	1	1	3	48	4
Bhagwanpur II	-	-	1	2	6	9	95	4
Ramnagar I	1	-	1	3	4	9	90	14
Ramnagar II	-	-	1	3	-	4	30	11
Contai I	-	-	1	2	-	3	25	7
Deshapran	-	-	1	2	-	3	10	7
Contai III	-	-	1	2	-	3	10	5
Tamluk (M)	1	-	-	-	31	32	766	52
Haldia (M)	1	-	-	-	2	2	40	3
Egra (M)	1	-	-	-	14	15	512	29
Contai (M)	1	-	-	-	13	14	279	17
Contai (M)	1	-	-	-	11	12	340	30
TOTAL	5	3	22	51	132	213	3486	296

Source: Dy. C.M.O.H. - II, Purba Medinipur, Super / Director of the respective (L.S.G. / Private) hospitals, 2014, Super / Director of the respective hospitals, 2014 and calculated by the author.